

Supplemental Tables

Table S1. International Classification of Diseases and Related Health Problems (ICD)-9 Codes for Excluded Endocrinopathy.

Endocrinopathy	ICD-9 Code
Malignant neoplasm of corpus uteri, except isthmus	182.0
Goiter, specified as simple	240.0
Goiter, unspecified	240.9
Nontoxic unimodular goiter	241.0
Nontoxic multinodular goiter	241.1
Thyrotoxicosis with or without goiter	242
Congenital hypothyroidism	243
Acquired hypothyroidism	244
Thyroiditis	245
Other disorders of thyroid	246
Cushing's syndrome	255.0
Hyperaldosteronism	255.1
Adrenogenital disorders	255.3
Other corticoadrenal overactivity	255.3
Corticoadrenal insufficiency	255.4
Other adrenal hypofunction	255.5
Medulloadrenal hyperfunction	255.6
Other specified disorders of adrenal glands	255.8
Unspecified disorder of adrenal glands	255.9
Other ovarian dysfunction	256.8

Table S2. Effect estimates from logistic models estimating the probability of missed diagnosis by age, race/ethnicity, education, and insurance type among those who meet the criteria for PCOS diagnosis (N = 1,929) including multiplicative interaction terms for insurance type and race/ethnicity, for women aged 18 to 45 attending Boston Medical Center between 2003 and 2015.

Term	β estimate (SE)	p-value
Race/ethnicity (Ref = White)		
Black/African American	0.734 (0.359)	<0.001
Hispanic/Latino	0.288 (0.321)	0.37
Other	0.205 (0.258)	0.43
Education (Ref = College or postgrad)		
Some high school or less	-0.004 (0.136)	0.98
Graduated high school or GED	0.108 (0.132)	0.42
Other	-0.286 (0.189)	0.13
Insurance type (Ref = Private)		
Charity	1.540 (0.357)	<0.001
Medicaid	0.742 (0.257)	0.004
Other	-0.104 (0.548)	0.85
Body mass index (Ref = Under/normal weight)		
Overweight	-0.349 (0.168)	0.04
Obese	-0.963 (0.161)	<0.001
Class III Obese	-1.409 (0.181)	<0.001
Language (Ref = English)		
Other	0.284 (0.137)	0.04
Social Vulnerability Index Score (per 10% increase)	0.046 (0.035)	0.18
Insurance type * Race/ethnicity		
Charity * Black/African American	-1.047 (0.407)	0.01
Charity * Hispanic/Latino	-1.390 (0.514)	0.007
Charity * Other Race	-0.752 (0.496)	0.13
Medicaid * Black/African American	-0.180 (0.310)	0.56
Medicaid * Hispanic/Latino	-0.130 (0.423)	0.76
Medicaid * Other Race	-0.191 (0.415)	0.65
Other insurance * Black/African American	0.189 (0.616)	0.76
Other insurance * Hispanic/Latino	0.057 (0.775)	0.94
Other insurance * Other Race	-0.041 (0.857)	0.96

Coefficients with p < 0.05 are shown in bold.

Table S3. Study participants (n) by race/ethnicity category and insurance type.

	Private	Charity	Medicaid	Other
White	282	46	123	21
Black/African American	233	210	378	76
Hispanic/Latino	68	80	119	24
Other	124	55	75	15

Table S4. Odds ratios for probability of missed diagnosis by age, race/ethnicity, education, and insurance type among those who meet the criteria for PCOS diagnosis (N = 1,929) for women aged 18 to 45 attending Boston Medical Center between 2003 and 2015 (Figure 3).

Variable	Odds Ratio Univariate model	Odds Ratio Fully adjusted ^a model	Odds Ratio Fully adjusted ^a model + SVI
	e^{β} (95% CI)	e^{β} (95% CI)	e^{β} (95% CI)
Age (IQR 10 years)	1.39 (1.20, 1.60)	1.52 (1.30, 1.78)	1.53 (1.30, 1.79)
Race/Ethnicity			
White	Ref	Ref	Ref
Black/African American	1.97 (1.55, 2.50)	1.86 (1.43, 2.43)	1.75 (1.33, 2.31)
Non-white Hispanic/Latino	1.23 (0.90, 1.70)	1.06 (0.75, 1.50)	1.01 (0.70, 1.44)
Other	1.26 (0.91, 1.73)	1.23 (0.80, 1.58)	1.11 (0.79, 1.57)
Highest Education			
Some college/voc/tech program	Ref	Ref	Ref
Some high school or less	1.34 (1.06, 1.69)	1.05 (0.81, 1.36)	1.04 (0.80, 1.36)
Graduated high school or GED	1.25 (0.99, 1.58)	1.18 (0.92, 1.53)	1.16 (0.90, 1.50)
Other	0.72 (0.51, 1.00)	0.74 (0.51, 1.06)	0.74 (0.52, 1.07)
Insurance Type			
Private	Ref	Ref	Ref
Medicaid	1.80 (1.45, 2.25)	1.95 (1.52, 2.51)	1.90 (1.47, 2.45)
Charity	2.10 (1.62, 2.71)	1.91 (1.43, 2.55)	1.86 (1.39, 2.50)
Other	1.28 (0.87, 1.89)	1.15 (0.76, 1.73)	1.12 (0.74, 1.69)
Year dx (IQR 6 years)	0.72 (0.62, 0.84)	0.67 (0.56, 0.79)	0.67 (0.56, 0.79)

Language			
English	Ref	Ref	Ref
Other	1.56 (1.24, 1.96)	1.35 (1.04, 1.75)	1.33 (1.02, 1.73)
BMI			
Underweight/normal	Ref	Ref	Ref
Overweight	0.75 (0.56, 1.02)	0.68 (0.49, 0.94)	0.68 (0.49, 0.94)
Obese	0.54 (0.41, 0.71)	0.39 (0.29, 0.54)	0.39 (0.29, 0.53)
Class III Obese	0.36 (0.26, 0.50)	0.25 (0.18, 0.35)	0.25 (0.17, 0.35)
Standardized Social Vulnerability Index Score (10% increase)	1.12 (1.06, 1.19)	-	1.05 (0.98, 1.12)

^aModel includes age, race/ethnicity, education, and insurance type.

Table S5. Odds ratios for probability of missed diagnosis by social vulnerability index scores among those who meet the criteria for PCOS diagnosis (N = 1,929) for women aged 18 to 45 attending Boston Medical Center between 2003 and 2015 (Figure 4).

Social Vulnerability Variable	Unadjusted effect estimate	Fully adjusted^a effect estimate
	Estimated mean change (95% <i>CI</i>)	Estimated mean change (95% <i>CI</i>)
Standardized Social Vulnerability Index Score (total)	1.12 (1.06, 1.19)	1.05 (0.98, 1.12)
Standardized Social Vulnerability Index Score: Socioeconomic Factor	1.07 (1.03, 1.12)	1.02 (0.98, 1.07)
Standardized Social Vulnerability Index Score: Household Composition/Disability Factor	1.04 (1.01, 1.08)	1.00 (0.95, 1.04)
Standardized Social Vulnerability Index Score: Minority Status/ Language Factor	1.10 (1.05, 1.16)	1.03 (0.97, 1.09)
Standardized Social Vulnerability Index Score: Housing Type/Transportation Factor	1.12 (1.05, 1.20)	1.09 (1.01, 1.18)

^aModel includes age, race/ethnicity, education, and insurance type.